

ISSUES OF ORGANIZATION OF PSYCHOLOGICAL SERVICE IN A PERSON-ORIENTED EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. *This article describes the role and importance of the psychologist's activity as an effective method of spiritual education of young people in the conditions of globalization of the world.*

Keywords: *spirituality, influence, globalization, education, upbringing, psychological influence, psychologist's activity, spiritual immunity, control, society, nationality, threats.*

In the developed countries of the world, especially in the People's Republic of China, Japan, Korea, and other countries, the efforts to preserve national traditions are significantly noticeable, and such actions have become the level of state priority policy. Because the main goal of this is to preserve the identity and ensure the guaranteed future of the nation.

In our country, the urgent importance of organizing psychological services in a person-oriented educational environment has become a priority of our state. Especially in recent decades, such actions have been taking place significantly. As a clear example of this, the establishment and rapid development of the activity of the inspector psychologist in the general education schools of our country serves as the basis of our opinion. In addition, we can say that education of young people in the national spirit, joint education and upbringing in the course of the lesson is included in the state program.

In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-27 of February 28, 2023, we can see a quality mechanism for the future of our country and nation, human interests, moral and ideological immunity, issues of organization, and the basis of quality education, maintaining nationality, in addition to the concepts of human interests and quality education.

In the conditions of today's globalization, the only way to face threats that do not choose borders is to organize psychological services in a person-oriented educational environment, and the role of competitive personnel in this process is incomparable. It is not a secret that today, in the conditions of global globalization, there are issues of creating a modern educational environment, problems of creating a quality educational environment, and problems of adapting the mentality of students in the classroom system based on new technologies, and preventing possible stress and depression.

Although individual-oriented education is recognized as a guarantee of quality education in our society, the issues of education and upbringing have always been taken seriously, showing the importance of gathering and forming the minds of young people on the basis of one idea. Therefore, the issues of organizing psychological services in a person-oriented educational environment are considered a guarantee of more effective development of today's quality education.

Problem situations that may arise in the modern educational environment focused on individuals as educational participants are as follows			
Participants	Situations	Reasons	Results
Among teachers	Inability to accept a new environment,	That's enough for me, to avoid additional responsibilities,	Loss of work on oneself, apathy
Among teachers and students	Not being able to get the right answer, not being able to adapt in terms of equality of opinions, cases of multiplication of unfounded opinions	Lack of time, inability to accept periodic age development,	Distancing of the system of relations between the teacher and students
Among students and students	Not taking into account each other's opinions, cases of personal discrimination	Striving for leadership, putting oneself above others	There is a situation of classification among students
From the above cases, we can say that in creating a modern person-oriented educational environment, the organization of psychological services has a potential effect on the elimination of today's educational problems. Because in this process, the subject who connects the relationship between the teacher and the teacher, the relationship between the teacher and the students, and the relationship between the student and the students is definitely a psychologist, and in this process, the psychologist acts as a bridge in a comparative sense.			

In connection with the organization of psychological services in a person-oriented educational environment, a practicing psychologist should pay special attention to the development of recommendations and approaches to the participants of education based on the situation, and also pay attention to the effective methods of interaction.

It is important to pay attention to the following in the process of psychological influence and studying the child.

- Taking into account the ethnopsychological situation - mainly taking into account the factors of the formation of the environment in which the child lives. We know that the factor of social formation has a great influence on the regularity of the child's mental development.
- Taking into account the system of family relations (family types, low income or vice versa, real or premature orphan status, number of children in the family and similar situations) - it is necessary not to forget that the main factor and fundamental system of education is the family.
- Taking into account the influence of biological and genetic factors on personality development - in this process, the transfer of character traits, diseases, and imitability from generation to generation.
- Taking into account the system of the person's relationship with the team - the level of interpersonal communication and communication skills.

- Taking into account the system of self-evaluation and the concept of self - in this process, the emergence of ideas about oneself, a person's ideas about the world around him, the things he wants to do and dreams, the attitude of the world around him to the person the relationship that emerged through.
- Taking into account the person's attitude towards adults and children.

From the perspective of a leading psychologist, building a culture of communication based on the above principles and establishing communication is one of the effective ways to achieve the desired result.

In conclusion, we can say that the issue of closely linking educational reform with the organization of psychological services in a person-oriented educational environment is a requirement of the time and society, and this is a guarantee for the establishment of a quality educational environment, competitive personnel potential and a stable society. In this process, the role of psychology in terms of direct influence is incomparable. The promotion of psychology depends more on the psychological staff and their potential levels in educational and public organizations. Here, it is important to consider the following.

Improvement of programs aimed at increasing the qualifications of psychologists in the implementation of issues of organization of psychological services in a person-oriented educational environment in a manner specific to the requirements of the time.

Expanding the authority and staff of psychologists working in educational and public organizations in improving the organization of psychological services in a person-oriented educational environment and implementing an effective method.

Development of measures to improve cooperation between psychologists in the implementation of psychological service organization in a person-oriented educational environment.

REFERENCES

1. Ibraimov X. I va Quronov M "Umumiy pedagogika" darslik –T., "Sahhof", 2023, 416 bet
2. Xoliqov A.A; Pedagogik mahorat: Pedagogika va psixologiya ta'lim yo'nalishining talabarlari (o'quvchilari) uchun darslik. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy va o'rta maxsus ta'lim vazirligi. T.: «iqtisod-moliya», 2011.432 b.
3. Egamnazarov M.Yu. Pedagogika va psixologiya ta'lim yo'nalishi talabalarida kommunikativ qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish. // Xalq ta'limi O'zbekiston Respublikasi Xalq ta'limi vazirligining ilmiy-metodik jurnali – Toshkent, 2020. № 5. – B. 83-86.
4. Ibraimov Kh. I. Creativity as one of the characteristics of the personality of the future teacher // Science, education and culture. – 2018. – no. 3 (27). - P. 44-46
5. Ibragimovich Kh.I. Peculiarities of using credit-module technologies in the higher education system of Uzbekistan //Integration of science, education and practice. Scientific-methodical journal. - 2021. - P. 209-214.
6. Ibraimov Kh. "Theoretical and methodological basis of quality control and evaluation of education in higher education system." International journal of discourse on innovation, integration and education 1 (2020): 6-15.
7. Ibragimov, X., Abdullayeva Sh. "Pedagogika nazariyasi (darslik)." T.: Fan va texnologiya 288 (2008).

8. Ibraimov X.I., M.Quronov. Umumiy pedagogika (darslik). –Т., “Shaffof”, 2023, 416-bet.
9. Ibragimovich I. K. et al. PEDAGOGICAL ABILITIES OF A TEACHER, STRUCTURE AND DEVELOPMENT //湖南大学学报 (自然科学版). – 2021. – Т. 48. – №. 12.
10. Ибрагимов Х. И. ПЕДАГОГИКА И ВОСПИТАНИЕ //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 1-1 (80). – С. 608-611.
11. Ibragimovich, Ibraimov Kholboy. "Intensive methods of teaching foreign languages at university." Вопросы науки и образования 27 (39) (2018): 78-80.
12. Ибраимов Х. И. Педагогические и психологические особенности обучения взрослых //Academy. – 2019. – №. 10 (49). – С. 39-41.
13. Ибрагимов Х. И. Организация самостоятельной работы студентов в условиях цифровизации вузовского образования //Наука и образование сегодня. – 2020. – №. 7 (54). – С. 74-75.